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Contextual Privacy Preservation in Active and Assisted Living Using Omnidirectional Cameras

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Abstract

This paper explores contextual privacy preservation using top-view omnidirectional dioptric cameras, particularly within Active and Assisted Living (AAL) environments. These technologies hold significant promise for enhancing the quality of life for older adults and individuals with disabilities, yet they also introduce substantial privacy challenges. Using the concept of "Privacy by Context" based on Nissenbaum's theory of contextual integrity, this paper proposes a privacy-preserving pipeline for omnidirectional cameras that aligns with EU legal frameworks. As part of the research, the ODIN dataset was created to facilitate the creation of machine learning models aimed at scene understanding with omnidirectional dioptric camera images..

Introduction

Active and Assisted Living (AAL) technologies have immense potential to enhance the lives of older adults and individuals with disabilities by supporting daily

activities, health monitoring, and emergency assistance. However, integrating advanced imaging systems like omnidirectional cameras into personal spaces raises significant privacy concerns, potentially hindering user acceptance and adoption.

Contextual Integrity, a privacy framework proposed by Nissenbaum (2009), suggests that privacy is preserved when information flows adhere to the norms of specific social contexts, considering factors such as actors, transmission principles, and information types. Building on this, the concept of "Privacy by Context" emphasizes designing systems that respect these contextual norms, while "Privacy by Design" (Cavoukian, 2009) advocates incorporating privacy considerations into system architecture from the outset. Despite these frameworks, effectively implementing privacy-preserving mechanisms for omnidirectional imaging in AAL environments remains a challenge. This research aims to develop an end-to-end privacy-preserving pipeline for omnidirectional RGB cameras in AAL settings, compliant with EU legal regulations like the GDPR.

Research Questions

The goal of this research is to create an end-to-end privacy-preserving pipeline for omnidirectional RGB cameras in AAL settings that complies with EU legal regulations. Three research questions were formulated and explored as part of the research.

1. **RQ1:** Can contextual visual privacy be provided for individuals appearing in RGB images?
2. **RQ2:** Can privacy be maintained for individuals observed in zenithal-view dioptric omnidirectional camera images?
3. **RQ3:** Can a privacy by design pipeline be created for omnidirectional images adhering to legal regulations?

A taxonomy of visual Privacy Enhancing Technologies

The research involved developing a low-level taxonomy of Visual Privacy Enhancing Technologies aligning with the privacy by design elements at five different levels proposed in Mihailis and Colonna (2020): sensor, model, system, UI, and user. The proposed low-level taxonomy operates at five associated levels as well, namely Visual Obfuscation, Data Hiding, Secure Processing, Blind Vision, and Intervention methods. Further subdivisions of visual obfuscation technologies are also explored.

It was determined that in order to achieve visual privacy by design, a pipeline should provide privacy at all all five different levels of the schema. Particular emphasis was given to visual obfuscation methods, which operate at the UI level.

The pipeline proposed by Climent-Pérez and Florez-Revuelta (2021) was chosen as a foundation due to its comprehensive approach to privacy preservation in RGB images, involving segmentation masks, 3D pose estimates, and background processing. However, since this pipeline was designed for standard RGB images, it was adapted to accommodate the unique characteristics of top-view dioptic omnidirectional camera images. This involves the development of specialized models for semantic segmentation and 3D pose estimation that can handle the distortion and wide field of view inherent to omnidirectional images.

The creation of semantic segmentation and 3D pose estimation models for the omnidirectional pipeline required data that included associated pose and semantic segmentation labels for associated top-view omnidirectional images. This proved difficult as such data was scarce. The ODIN dataset was created for this purpose.

ODIN Dataset

The ODIN (OmniDirectional INdoor) dataset by Ravi et al. (2023) was developed to address the scarcity of data for training machine learning models. This dataset captures activities of daily living in real living and working settings with multiple synchronized modalities, including top-view omnidirectional and lateral-view RGB images, infrared and depth images captured from calibrated cameras. It captures a wide range of activities of daily living performed by 15 participants, providing rich annotations for scene understanding tasks such as pose estimation and semantic segmentation. ODIN also provides further labels and annotations making it suitable for other tasks as varied as activity recognition, 3D reconstruction and person tracking.

Legal Considerations and Challenges

The legal landscape, particularly the GDPR, presents challenges for Privacy Enhancing Technologies (PETs), as most are considered pseudonymisation due to their reversible nature. The research highlights the need for concrete guidelines on privacy by design under EU data protection laws. The EU AI Act is a step in the right direction. Mihaildis and Colonna (2020) provide the most comprehensive approach for integrating privacy into system design from inception.

Ongoing and Future Work

Ongoing work involves training lightweight models for pose estimation and semantic segmentation using the ODIN dataset and integrating them into the

privacy by design pipeline. Collaborative efforts are also underway to develop activity recognition models using omnidirectional images.

Conclusion

This research advances the development of a privacy by design system for top-view omnidirectional cameras in AAL environments, addressing the critical need for contextual privacy preservation. By proposing a comprehensive taxonomy of visual privacy enhancing technologies and creating the ODIN dataset, we provide essential tools for developing and evaluating privacy-preserving models suitable for omnidirectional images.

This work not only contributes to technological innovation but also ensures compliance with legal frameworks, paving the way for the responsible deployment of AAL technologies. While challenges remain, particularly in optimizing models for real-time applications and expanding legal guidelines, our ongoing efforts aim to bridge these gaps. Ultimately, this research opens novel directions in the field of omnidirectional scene understanding with strong privacy guarantees.

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